

Welcome to the survey of the University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna and Freie Universität Berlin

Thank you for taking time to participate in this scientific survey. We would like to evaluate the opinion and acceptance of students of veterinary medicine and agricultural sciences on the use of sensor systems in dairy cattle farming and thus create a basis for discussions on this topic.

This study is also part of a PhD project.

Many thanks again,

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- Gender clause: To improve readability, only the male or female form of personal nouns and pronouns are used: farmer, veterinarian. These terms are intended to be gender-neutral and apply equally to individuals of all genders. The choice of wording does not imply any form of discrimination.

Introduction

Technology in dairy farming

Technology and digitalization determine our professional and private everyday life. Digital technologies are also increasingly being used in dairy farming. These can capture a wide range of information on the health, behavior and performance of cows and help to improve the management of dairy cows. This serves the individual animal, the herd and the farmer.

We present three examples used in dairy farming.

1. **Automatic milking systems (AMS) and milking parlors:** With the AMS, the cow can choose when to be milked. In contrast, with a milking parlor, the cows must be brought in twice a day for milking. AMS provide animals with more free time management, while giving farmers greater flexibility in their work.
2. **Observation of the calving pen with video:** Video cameras are commonly used in the calving pen. This area in the barn is usually straw-bedded and offers the cow an optimal environment for calving. The videos are transferred to the farmer's mobile phone or computer. This allows the farmer to check at any time, even at night, whether the dam or calf need help.
3. **Automatic feed pusher:** Constant accessibility of feed is important for cows. Therefore, feed must be replenished several times during the day. This can be done by an automatic feed pusher and is a physical relief for farmer.

Automatic milking system

Video camera

Automated feed push

Let's start the survey now!

1. Gender:
 - male
 - female
 - diverse
2. Study discipline:
 - Veterinary medicine
 - Agricultural sciences
3. Where do you study?

4. Current semester (please indicate the number of the semester you are currently enrolled in):

5. Place of origin (please indicate your home location, not your place of study):

- in a village in a rural community
- in a village near the city
- in a small town (up to 30,000 inhabitants)
- in a city of medium size up to 100,000 inhabitants
- in a big city up to 500,000 inhabitants
- in a big city with over 500,000 inhabitants

6. Besides your studies, what is your current connection to dairy farming? (Multiple answers possible)

- Dairy farming in the family or among friends
- I come from a rural area
- Vacations on a farm or similar activities
- No connection

7. How would you rate your own level of knowledge about today's dairy farming?

- very good
- good
- moderate
- bad
- no answer

8. How do you feel about the following everyday technologies?

Everyday technologies	I would definitely use it	I can well imagine using it	I am skeptical about using it	Use is out of question for me	No statement
Smartwatch					
Fitness or health trackers					
Voice assistants ("Alexa", "Siri", or others)					
Smart home systems					

9. Today, we can also equip our cows with "fitness trackers" (sensors), as shown here in the images (green arrow). These provide a wide range of information and can support farmers, for example, in identifying sick animals or animals that are due to breed.

10. What do you think about such "fitness trackers" for cows?

- I like it. Technological progress benefits humans and animals.
- I find it acceptable if it improves animal health.
- I do not like it. There is already too much technology in the barn.
- It is not necessary. The farmer knows his animals best.
- Not specified.

11. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? Please mark the appropriate box

Statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Slightly agree	Do not agree	No statement
I can imagine that with too much technology the bond between farmer and cow gets lost.					
I would like milk produced without much technology.					
I can imagine that detecting problems in cows is easier with technical aids.					
Artificial intelligence increases my confidence in agriculture.					
Organic farming and digitalization do not go together.					

12. Which objective should take priority when using digital technologies in agriculture? (Ranking from 1-6, 1 is the most important objective for you)

- More animal welfare
- Reduction of greenhouse gases
- Conservation of resources
- Reduction in the use of medication
- Improvement of the work-life balance for farmers
- Maintenance of the international competitiveness of domestic agriculture

13. Digital technologies are currently being promoted in agriculture. Do you think digital technologies in agriculture deserve support? (Multiple answers possible)

- Yes, if it serves animal welfare.
- Yes, if it serves to increase production.
- Yes, if it serves to maintain the location of the agricultural sector.
- No.
- Not specified.

14. The quality of agricultural products is mainly assured by the decisions made by farmers. Digital technologies can assist them in this. To what extent do you agree with the following statements? Please mark with a cross where applicable

	Strongly agree	Agree	Slightly agree	Do not agree	Not specified
I tend to trust the farmer's experience. Technology should only support farmer's decisions.					
Product quality can be significantly improved by new technologies (e.g. sensors).					
To ensure product quality and animal welfare, the farmer should primarily rely on the support of the veterinarian.					
New technologies will change the way farmers and veterinarians work and thus improve product quality.					

15. Please look at this image.

The image depicts the barn office of a farmer who utilizes barn-installed sensors to collect data, which he then evaluates to support herd management decisions. What comes to mind when viewing this image? Please write down two to three terms.

16. Please look at another image.

The image depicts a calf receiving milk through an automatic calf feeder. What associations come to mind when viewing this image? Please write down two to three terms.

17. What terms do you associate with modern dairy farming? Write down 2 to 3 terms!

18. Do you see modern dairy farming in a positive or negative light?

19. What do you think dairy farming **should** look like in the future? Write down 2 to 3 terms!

20. What do you think dairy farming **will** look like in the future? Write down 2 to 3 terms!

21. Do you consider yourself adequately prepared for the digital transformation in dairy farming as a result of your college education?

Thank you for participating in my scientific survey!